

ECONOMIC GLOBALIZATION – DIMENSIONS AND HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract:

In this paper, we approach a chronological analysis of globalization from an economic dimension. We know this term of globalization has become increasingly used since the 1990s. The phenomenon of globalization as well as its effects are subject to many analyzes quantifying both the socio-economic advantages and disadvantages. However, far fewer have focused on a historical analysis of economic globalization. Starting from the definition of globalization - a process by which economies become more and more interconnected and interdependent – can we assert that globalization has its origins in the mists of history with the occurrence and development of the silk road? Although there are many opinions about when globalization began, we believe that based on the arguments presented in this research, the trade routes created during the Silk Road represent an important moment in the history and beginnings of globalization. Throughout history, socio-economic events such as the first industrial revolution and the current digital revolution have led to the evolution of trade routes and the emergence of new technologies that have transformed the nature of trade.

Keywords: Globalization, Trade, Silk Road, Economic Growth, Development

JEL classification: F40, F60, N00

1. Introduction

Globalization is considered an irreversible process characterized by an increasing interconnection of national economies, a growth in international investment and trade flows, a greater integration of financial markets, and an increase in international labor mobility. This increase in interdependence between countries and regions has also generated an acceleration of social, cultural, political, and economic changes on a global level.

Today, globalization is seen as a controversial issue, and its advantages and disadvantages are the subject of ongoing debates.

The 21st century is the century of extremes in which humanity experienced the most spectacular developments knowing the highest level of economic and cultural development, but it is also the century in which millions of people were victims of wars, economic, political, scientific, ethnic or religious cleansing.

In this context, we bring up the phenomenon of globalization - a concept used to characterize the current state of the world economy but understood differently by academics, researchers in different fields: economics, history, sociology, etc.

Although set at the end of the century and the millennium, the phenomenon of globalization has a long history behind it. From a historical point of view, globalization represents the consequence of the increasingly accelerated development of societies since the first industrial revolution. (Stearns, 2019)

The question that has not found an answer widely accepted among historians is: when did globalization appear? The period 1492-1498 is considered to be the beginning of the globalization period when Vasco de Gama circumnavigated Africa. (McNeill, 2017)

We also discover in the rich literature dedicated to this vast subject, the idea the idea according to which the peak period of globalization was in the Victorian era, when the free movement of production factors and the movement of labor were intensified. (Germain, 2000)

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Other historians, and not a few, believe, however, that the 19th century was the cradle of globalization, knowing a great momentum in the second half of the 20th century, although the terminology known today it was used on a large scale only in the 1990s.

Globalization as a process has been generated by a number of forces. The worldwide expansion of capitalism and technological progress underlies the dynamics of globalization. These forces have made their mark depending on the socio-economic context but have increased intensity in recent decades.

Globalization process has been associated with widespread socio-economic consequences. In many cases, they have been highlighted

by the fact that the current phase of accelerated globalization - beginning in the 1970s - has coincided with declining economic growth activity in parts of the industrial countries and stagnation and decline in many countries in Latin America, Africa, the Middle East and some Asian countries.

At the same time, globalization has been associated with a number of other changes, such as technological progress, liberalization and deregulation. It is quite impossible to separate the economic impacts of globalization, however defined, from those of previous factors.

Most researches of this globalization that argue that the origins of this phenomenon is in the mists of time, although there are different opinions regarding the exactness of the starting point. To a certain extent world history can be seen as a dynamic phenomenon tending towards ever larger social systems, towards their integration and globalization.

Other questions concern the zero point of globalization, the chronological placement before or after the era of great discoveries. We know that even before the great geographical discoveries there were socio-economic ties but in a rather limited sense. Therefore, the previously existing channels of communication are considered to be insignificant in the debate of this topic.

Certainly, it is difficult to answer this question, and no doubt the historical dimension of globalizations is a huge challenge for all those involved in debate this phenomenon. (Habich, 2017)

2. Literature review

In the research field, there are numerous sociological, economic, anthropological, political studies that analyze globalization under its many dimensions and at the same time attempt a chronology of this complex and increasingly disputed phenomenon.

Although the term globalization is relatively new, people, cultures, peoples from different times were interconnected long before the term globalization was enshrined in media and academic language.

It is believed that the philosopher Hegel was the first theorist of globalization when he talks in his philosophy about the world-spirit concept, imagining all humanity as a single community.(Eriksen, 2014)

At the end of the 90s, (Frank, 1998) associates the beginning of globalization much earlier - during the Pax Mongolica period, a term that describes the effects of the conquests of the Mongol Empire and the effects on the social and economic life of the inhabitants of the conquered Eurasian territory in the 13th and 14th centuries th. Also the term pax mongolica is used to describe the communication and commercial channels maintained by the then existing administration contributing to the creation and maintenance of a month long period of peace.

One of the first authors who dedicated many pages to this controversial subject, intuited since the 2000s that the process of globalization is not a passing trend. He sees the globalization of an international system that has replaced the Cold War, and that the movement of capital and technology across national borders into a global economic system. (Friedman, 2000)

Even today, almost a quarter of a century after the publication of his book, research from an economic, historical, sociological point of view considers the two relevant aspects of Friedman: the desire for integration that involves prosperity and socio-economic development symbolized on the one hand by Lexus and on the other hand the preservation of identity and traditions unaltered by the effects of globalization symbolized by the olive tree.

The term globalization was used in English around the 1930s without raising too many questions. However, starting from the 1990s, when the macroeconomic climate changed considerably, the term globalization is increasingly used in most discussions and the phenomenon of globalization is debated in academic circles as well as in scientific research (Eriksen, 2014). One of the limitations of scientific research on this subject refers to its origin, the development and modification of the concept of globalization in relation to the economic texture of then and today (McNeill, 2017).

According to Ogar (2018), globalization is seen as a powerful and invisible god of the universe with both positive and negative implications for human condition. Globalization is an irreversible process that unfolds in full accordance with the laws of nature.

Some highlight the fact that the phenomenon of globalization has roots that are both non-Western and Western. Many authors, who support this view, pay particular attention, in terms of the evolution of globalization, to China, South Asia, Islamic countries, Europe, and the United States. (Keohane, 2000)

In the book, *Globalization: A multi-dimensional system*, (Gopinath 2023) considers that those who analyze the phenomenon of globalization from all perspectives can be classified into three categories of analysts: hyperglobalizers, skeptics, and transformationalists. The hyperglobalizers are those who believe that with the phenomenon of globalization, we have entered a new era, and each of us becomes subject to a set of rules within a single global market. The skeptics are those who argue that the phenomenon of globalization is not unprecedented from a historical standpoint, states are still powerful, and there are significant regional trade blocs in the global economy. The third category of researchers, the transformationalists, see globalization as a new phenomenon full of contradictions that can bring unprecedented major changes at the state level. Moreover, they consider the nature of the phenomenon of globalization as uncertain and without a predictable end.

According to (Umezina, 2022 and Kanu, 2014), analyzing the phenomenon of globalization in the context of African culture, the question of whether Africans should join the globalization wagon is a complex one. Examining the benefits that Africa could have derived from globalization, such as increased trade, investment, job creation, and poverty reduction, it appears that none of these have materialized. Despite Africa's abundant resources, economic progress and development remain elusive. The author concludes that Africa should not be an integral part of the global market, as most countries in Africa have not experienced economic progress and development. Another reason given is that globalization limits the freedom and equality of individuals.

The question of when globalization began is not the most accurate, especially if connectivity is its central element, as connections have been part of human history since the beginning (Nederveen 2012).

According to another author the Industrial Revolution brought about enormous economic, social, and political changes, such as progress in agriculture and transportation, mass production of goods with visible effects on the global expansion of commercial relations, and increased employment. During this period, the GDP per capita of European and North American countries increased significantly. (Mohajan (2019)

Globalization is commonly regarded as a new phenomenon, but contact between different individuals is not new. It began when prehistoric tribes settled and managed to dominate nomadic tribes through force. (Steger, 2013)

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3. Theoretical framework and methodology

This scientific research focuses on the phenomenon of globalization, its dimensions, and its chronology to demonstrate that it is an ancient phenomenon whose roots can be traced back to the opening of the Silk Road.

To define this idea, the research aimed to answer several questions based on the definition of globalization: can we place the origins of globalization with the opening of the Silk Road, and how has it evolved over the centuries up to today? The research combines multiple methods of methodology, primarily relying on qualitative analysis.

In order to find answers to the issues addressed in this scientific paper, a sufficient number of documents and scientific articles were analyzed, with the most representative ones encountered in this research, which examined globalization from various perspectives: its history, positive and negative effects, as well as its limitations.

To enhance the research results, the phenomenon was also studied from a statistical point of view, analyzing the historical evolution of the gross domestic product (GDP) by regions and continents from 1 AD to 2021.

In the author's opinion, globalization is more than just an interconnectedness of the world's economies, and it did not begin either at the beginning of the 20th century or in the mid-1970s. As for the three or four stages of globalization, they are natural transformations imposed by the changes that the global socio-economic context has experienced throughout history.

This form of globalization is considered by historians as archaic globalization and lasted for a long period, over 1000 years. The Silk Road was not a single road, but a complex network of roads that connected the largest empires of the time such as India, China, Rome, and Persia. During the peak period of the Silk Road, connections between regions of the world, commercial exchanges, as well as ancient Chinese inventions such as silk, the technique of raising silk worms, porcelain, gunpowder, compass, and producing paper intensified. At the same time, China received original goods from Europe in exchange. All these exchanges had an overwhelming influence on civilization and culture globally. Trade ceased to be a local or regional affair and began to become global. (Bright and Geyer, 2012)

Can we talk about a phenomenon of globalization during these times? The opinions among specialists are divided. Along with those who consider that the globalization phenomenon has undergone three major stages (1492-1800; 1800-2000; 2000-present), there are also, increasing numbers, who believe that this complex process of globalization began long before 1492, experiencing several stages, placing the origin of globalization with the development of commercial routes associated with the Silk Road and the development of commercial relations.

It is considered this first period of globalization either as the first stage of the phenomenon we are analyzing, or we can talk about an early or archaic globalization. (Sheffield, 2013)

Moreover, through comparative analysis, I was able to compare the globalization phenomenon in different periods of time and in different regions of the world, thus trying to identify general trends and differences in the chronology and development of globalization. With the help of economic analysis, I compared the total output by region and continent to highlight that the link between interdependence and gross domestic product has always existed. Finally, I chose an approach that focuses on the impact of globalization on society and culture, highlighting the importance of social interactions and cultural exchanges in a global context.

4. The evolution of economic globalization

Globalization of the world economy as a first definition is the integration of economies primarily through trade flows and later through other flows, today we can also talk about technological and human capital flows.

In the multitude of questions about the evolution of the globalization concept, we find answers from various chronological perspectives. Some researchers of the phenomenon believe that the first

phase of globalization coincides with the Greek polises and Phoenician colonies, where there were the most developed commercial routes and diverse economic activities. (McKeown, 2007)

The process of globalization becomes increasingly obviously when a growing share of global output is generated by international trade activity.

According to Maddison Historical Statistics, analyzing GDP growth from 1 to 1820 (fig.1), the region with the most significant growth was clearly Asia. The Asian continent benefited the most from the fact that the world's most important trade axis, the Silk Road, cross it for many centuries. The fact that Europe also recorded the second largest economic growth during this period, globally, indicates that certain flows, particularly between more developed economies, have developed, facilitating not only the circulation of goods but also a transfer of technologies (as they existed at that time).

The existence of the Silk Road was a true bridge between cultures and civilizations, a bridge that generated interconnection between regions, countries, and civilizations with significant effects on their development. It is not wrong to consider that during this period, we are dealing with a form of globalization, indeed a specific globalization of that period, an archaic, medieval globalization. (Thompson, 2021)

Figure 1: GDP evolution between 1-1820, dollars, constant prices (relative to 1990)

Source: <https://www.rug.nl/ggdc/historicaldevelopment/maddison/releases/maddison-database-2010>

We know that the Silk Road was a vast network of routes that connected different regions of the world. However, data from the same source, Maddison Historical Statistics, shows a low dynamic of GDP growth in Africa. This is due to the fact that although the Silk Road crossed the northern part of the African continent, the trade connections within it were much weaker compared to Europe or Asia.

Trade relations were intense between continents and regions that directly participated in transactions of various goods, such as Central Asia (Persians, Arabs) or Europe (Armenians, Greeks, Jews). Africa not only did not benefit from the trade in goods traded at that time, but also did not enjoy the cultural exchanges between civilizations and the inventions that appeared then. (Nayyar, 2019)

Asia, especially China, dominated international trade for a long time, but starting from the 16th century, control trade was taken over by Europeans. ((Nayyar, 2019)

With the era of the Great Discoveries, the trade of goods intensified, encompassing more and more territories. Moreover, there was an amazing development in the scientific field: astronomy, mechanics, physics. All these scientific discoveries made maritime transport increasingly easier, which was the basis for colonial domination by the Portuguese, Spanish, and later the Dutch and English. (Wang and Sun, 2021)

Although the discovery of America by Columbus is considered a great discovery, an equally significant discovery belongs to Portuguese explorer Ferdinand Magellan, who on the first

circumnavigation of the globe opened new routes to Indonesia, avoiding the trade routes controlled by Arabs and Italians.

Although at that time there was a vast network of roads and trade routes, global trade was at a low level. Thanks to the new discoveries, goods arrived in Europe that brought positive changes in people's lives (potatoes, sugar, tomatoes, coffee, etc.). Luxury goods such as silk or spices continued to be traded, but their prices experienced a significant decrease.

All these facts described above play an important role in understanding the phenomenon of globalization, even though some historians consider this period not to be one of globalization. We refer to the process of globalization and judging each period analyzed based on its own economic context but also on the existing socio-cultural texture at that time.

The centuries X-XV, a period with few material accumulations, nonetheless showed economic expansion in an agrarian society, diversification of economic activities, expansion of urban communities, and revitalization of not only local but also global trade. Additionally, in the centuries XV-XVIII, we encounter another economic texture in which trade truly becomes global and at the same time was the driving force behind the development of the European continent. (Charles, 2015)

Although the empires of that time had their own supply chains over quite large distances, the model of economic growth was still a colonial one. Global trade flourished during that period, with traded goods diversifying, in which a significant share was constituted by the trade of slaves. Unfortunately, the slave trade is indeed part of global history and the processes that have contributed to the formation of the global system we live in today. (Ron, 2022)

Although the new geographical discoveries opened up new trade routes between Europe, Africa, and America, which were used for the slave trade, this inhumane practice should not be confused with globalization itself, a practice that was ultimately abolished, but its effects continue to be felt in some countries until today.

The beginnings of the industrial revolution brought new processes and phenomena in the real economy that transformed society at the time. Capital shifted from the sphere of circulation to the sphere of production, becoming productive capital. Private initiative developed, being a solid foundation of economic individuals' freedom of action and decision. New discoveries and technological advances built the pillar of the birth of European hegemony, and we can assert that the industrial revolution is another solid foundation stone of globalization.

The end of the 18th century and the entire the 19th century represented a period of profound socio-economic transformations. The whole of Europe, especially Great Britain and France, faced powerful economic and social transformations as a result of the industrial revolution. Economic transformations as a result of industrialization also have social consequences. Now, outdated means of production are replaced by machines, and capital is increasingly invested in industries requiring large volumes of labor. In this way, England becomes more urbanized as peasants migrate to cities, forming the new working class. (Hsieh, 2002)

The demographic growth generated by the effects of industrialization brought about significant changes that Great Britain had to face. If until the end of the 18th century, England could cover its consumption needs from its own resources, starting from the 19th century, it had to import a considerable volume of resources.

Propelled by the industrial revolution, European empires began to expand, conquering one country after another and transforming them into colonies. In this way, Europeans opened up trade networks not only to bring raw materials and luxury goods to the continent but also to create markets for European products. The effects of industrialization crossed European borders, reaching the United States of America in a short time through European immigrants who brought their technology and industrial knowledge, and later through the development of local industrial technologies and innovations. This process contributed to the growth of the American economy and intensified the processes of globalization around the world. (Balogun, 2022)

Figure 2: Global gross domestic product per continent in 1820, 1870 and 1913 (in billion U.S. dollars)

Source: <https://www.statista.com/>

In the above figure, we can observe that during the period of 1820-1913, the peak period of socio-economic transformations generated by the Industrial Revolution, Europe experienced the most significant economic developments. The Industrial Revolution had a powerful impact on Europe's infrastructure and economic growth.

During this period of socio-economic changes, Europe benefited greatly from the effects of industrialization, becoming a world leader in technological innovations, from steam engines and telegraphy to the production of fertilizers and glass.

We also see a spectacular economic developments in Asia during this period. Despite the Europeans' colonization policy between 1650-1870, the economies of China and India made notable progress. The main vector in shaping intra-Asian and Asia-Europe trade was the East India Company, one of the most important commercial companies in history, which had a significant impact on the global economy and history, especially in terms of trade relations between Europe and Asia in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries. (Germain, 2000)

Although the Industrial Revolution had a much smaller impact on Asian countries, they produced major changes in economic, social, and cultural structures at a much slower pace than most countries in Europe and even North America. The interdependence between the two continents during and after the Industrial Revolution brought changes to both the goods traded, methods of trade and infrastructure. (Frank, 1998)

Africa continues to be passed by the effects of industrialization and the diversification of trade relations. Unfortunately, the period from the beginning of the eighteenth century to the middle of the twentieth century was marked by the colonization of Africa by European powers.

In the 20th century, the global economy experienced a spectacular economic growth, with the gross domestic product per capita increasing nearly five times compared to the previous century. The economic and financial structure of the century, especially in the second half, became increasingly complex, leading to an equally complex phenomenon of globalization. (Ron, 2022)

The complexity of the globalization process had a significant impact on the economy, culture, and international relations. This process led to an increase in trade and foreign investment, greater accessibility to cultures from around the world, and a shift in power relations worldwide.

Developed countries created their own industries but also attracted a large volume of foreign capital to finance other major investment projects. Moreover, globalization has led to an increase in economic inequality between developed and developing countries. (Karaduman, 2022)

We know that the phenomenon of globalization offers real opportunities for integration and economic development on a global level, but we also observe that not all countries are progressing uniformly.

Figure 3: GDP - current prices (2015), US dollars in millions (1970-2021)

Source: <https://unctad.org/>

In the above figure, we can see that the hierarchy of continents in terms of total GDP during the period of 1970-2021 doesn't differ much from the earlier analyzed periods. Countries that have integrated more easily into the global economy have experienced faster economic growth and a higher standard of living.

During the period at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, North America, particularly the United States, experienced significant economic growth, primarily through the development of industry. This process was fueled by a series of technological innovations, which made possible the mass production, the development of rail and maritime transport, major objective being the expanding markets and diversifying foreign trade. Economic and trade policies oriented towards openness brought prosperity not only to the North American continent but also to Asia, which in the last 20-25 years has become one of the most dynamic and prosperous regions in the world.

Countries that did not promote an economic policy of openness, particularly countries in South America and several countries in Africa, experienced economic stagnation and an increase in macroeconomic imbalances, leading to a very low standard of living.

Regarding Africa's globalization, it is recognized that this region has been insufficiently integrated into the global economy and that globalization could offer real opportunities for growth and development. The experience of globalization in recent decades highlights the fact that there is great untapped potential in African economies. (Bordo, 2002))

Economic globalization can bring a series of benefits to Africa, such as access to global markets and foreign direct investment, the transfer of technology and knowledge, as well as increased international trade. (ElGanainy, 2023 and Rodrik, 2018)

The phenomenon of globalization we see today aims to the same goal, only the process and tools differ because they are adapted to current social, economic, and technological conditions.

Furthermore, with the help of global digital infrastructure, the Chinese government intends to “rebuild” the old Silk Road - Digital Silk Road (DSR) - to create global connections between China, the Asia-Pacific, America, and Europe. The project that DSR falls under, the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), is a global project aimed at China's economic and commercial development through the creation of new digital infrastructure networks and the promotion and transfer of technology. DSR could offer

interconnected countries, especially in the Asia-Pacific region, significant economic opportunities and investment projects. (Agbebi, 2022)

5. Conclusions

Although the term globalization became common in the 1980s, the phenomenon of globalization viewed from an economic perspective is a historic process and refers to the increasing integration and interdependence of world economies through commercial and financial channels. Today, globalization also involves the circulation of information, knowledge, and human capital.

Globalization as a process is not just about connecting people, companies, and national economies. The purpose of this process refers to an expansion and interconnection of markets, promoting efficiency through competition and division of labor.

Economic globalization is a complex process that has had, is having, and will likely have a significant impact on the economy, culture, and international relations. It has generated over time an increase in trade and foreign investment, greater accessibility to cultures from around the world, and a shift in power relations globally.

Even long before the modern types of transportation (maritime, rail, and land), telecommunications (telegraphy, telephony), and digital communications, the movement of goods, people, and capital took place during the Silk Road. This was a complex commercial system that involved the transportation of goods, people, and the exchange of information. Through these trade routes, different communities in Asia, Europe, and the Middle East were directly connected and interacted economically. (Sotiriadis et al., 2017). During the Silk Road period, Asia was at the center of a trade network that extended from China to Europe and into North Africa. The trade of precious commodities such as silk, textiles, spices, herbs, and gemstones made Asia one of the most prosperous regions in the world.

Furthermore, this trade generated significant economic growth in many regions, and some cities became important commercial centers that prospered due to commercial activities. (Mussa, 2000)

This commercial and cultural interaction led to a change in relationships between communities from different parts of the world and opened the way for greater interdependence and collaboration. This can be seen as the beginning of the globalization process, which has evolved over time into more complex and sophisticated forms, especially in modern times, with the industrial revolution, communication technologies, and the development of global economies.

Regarding the movement of people, this was another important aspect of the Silk Road and we refer to explorers who discovered new territories that had an impact not only on the world culture but also on the later world economy.

The Silk Road was an important way to connect the economies of different regions of the early world and opened the way for greater economic and cultural interdependence between human communities.

The interconnection of economies through trade routes or other means of communication and transportation throughout the period analyzed generated risks and economic instability.

Unfortunately, today we still talk about the many risks of the globalization phenomenon. The phenomenon of contagion, a characteristic of globalization, represents the transmission of economic and financial shocks, both positive and negative.

In today's economic reality, in the context of economic globalization, we talk about financial globalization in addition to commercial globalization. In the current economic context, the financial system represents an increasingly important vector in the global economy, contributing to its dynamics. The role of the financial system was also not negligible in the Middle Ages or the Renaissance.

Globalization is seen both as an opportunity to eliminate the disparities that exist today and to make the great technological advances benefit not only the rich countries but also the poor countries that do not have access to them due to poverty. (Federico, 2016)

As mentioned, globalization is not a new phenomenon, it appeared long before the 20th century. What is new to us is the coat that the globalization process wears in relation to the socio-economic and cultural context of the period we are referring to. (Gill, 1995)

After World War II, globalization takes on a new form, with the rapid development of technology and communication systems, as well as the growth of international trade and foreign direct investment. During this period, people, goods, and ideas began to circulate more easily and quickly around the world, and the economic and cultural interdependence between countries and regions intensified.

The pre-modern period benefited technological advances that allowed commerce to flourish. The early modern period saw the birth of capitalism and regional markets. (Steger, 2013)

The contemporary era is an era of convergence, where people come together through deregulated economic and digital systems. (Steger, 2013)

Most scientific research on the phenomenon of globalization begins with defining this concept, referring to both its purpose and means, as well as its effects. Regardless of the authors's perspective, the definitions encountered in the specialized literature regarding globalization, from an economic perspective, are generally the same. Based on this, it has been demonstrated that the phenomenon of economic globalization, when viewed historically, began a long time ago, precisely with the discovery of the Silk Road. The personal viewpoints expressed above lead to the original contribution of this scientific research.

Although there are many opinions about when globalization began, we believe that based on the arguments presented in this research, we can affirm that it starting with the Silk Road, an important moment in the history of globalization, and continuing with subsequent events, global networks of trade and cultural exchanges were created. In parallel with the development of societies and economies, the globalization process has evolved continuously, accelerating according to technological, economic, political, and cultural changes. (Nobis, 2017 and Therborn, 2000)

Globalization as a phenomenon is not new, it is a complex process that cannot be reduced or framed only in a certain period. Starting with the Silk Road, continuing throughout the 15th-18th centuries, the global economy experienced an important period of economic globalization that shaped today's global economy.

Globalization is a multi-causal process that has generated social, economic, and cultural effects on a global scale. Today, the effects of globalization are transmitted almost in real-time due to technology and digital infrastructure, etc. Although during the Silk Road era and the subsequent period until the First Industrial Revolution, the effects were considerably delayed, this does not mean that the phenomenon underlying economic, social, and cultural connections cannot be rightfully called globalization.

Using statistical data on the evolution of the gross domestic product (GDP) by regions and continents from 1 AD to 2021, it was demonstrated that the Silk Road was a genuine bridge connecting cultures, civilizations, and economies of that time. Historical statistical data reflects that regions and continents situated along the Silk Road, such as Europe and Asia, experienced the highest economic growth. This fact highlights the dimension of the globalization phenomenon, suggesting that the primarily commercial flows that formed the basis of Europe's economic development also facilitated the transfer of technologies from that era. Today we know that globalization cannot exist outside economic freedom, therefore, we can assert that this form of globalization, whether we call it archaic globalization or proto-globalization, was accompanied by a similar form of capitalism.

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